

Metadata for “Asymmetric density-dependent competition and predation between larval salamanders”

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File: Anderson_Zoop.csv

Data for zooplankton communities in each tank.

Column information

Date: Date the tanks were sampled

Tank: Tank number

Initial_AMAN: Initial number of *A. annulatum*

Initial_AMOP: Initial number of *A. opacum*

CladPerL: Number of cladocerans per liter

CopePerL: Number of adult copepods per liter

OstraPerL: Number of ostracods per liter

RotifPerL: Number of rotifers per liter

JuvCopePerL: Number of juvenile copepods per liter

TotalZoopPerL: Total zooplankton per liter

File: Anderson_TankAvg.csv

Data on tank averages for salamanders in each tank

Column information

Tank: Tank number

Species: The species of salamander for morphometric traits

Initial_AMAN: Initial number of *A. annulatum*

Initial_AMOP: Initial number of *A. opacum*

Final_AMAN: Number of surviving *A. annulatum*

Final_AMOP: Number of surviving *A. opacum*

PercSurv_AMAN: Percent survival of *A. annulatum*

PercSurv_AMOP: Percent survival of *A. opacum*

meanSVL_meta: Mean metamorph snout-vent length (mm)
sdSVL_meta: Standard deviation of metamorph snout-vent length (mm)
meanMass_meta: Mean metamorph mass (g)
sdMass_meta: Standard deviation of metamorph mass (g)
meanDay_meta: Mean larval period length (days)
sdDay_meta: Standard deviation of larval period length (days)
meanTL_larv: Mean larval total length (mm)
sdTL_larv: Standard deviation of larval total length (mm)
meanHW_larv: Mean larval head width (mm)
sdTL_larv: Standard deviation of larval head width (mm)
SampleSize_larv: Number of larvae captured to obtain size measurements
NumLarvDead: Number of larvae found dead on lip of tank